

Designing reusable satellites for Europe

With the recent advent of large constellations of small satellites in Low Earth Orbit the problem of orbital debris has grown dramatically. Moreover, a typical satellite is very expensive and built only for a single mission. One way to reduce both costs and pollution in space is to do something that has never done before: design a satellite capable of operating in space, re-enter on Earth, be recovered and reused again multiple times. The EARS (European Advanced Reusable Satellite) project, funded by the European community through the Horizon program, has exactly this ambitious goal. The EARS project is led by CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche) and includes five other partners from all over Europe, including research centers, universities, small and large companies. UNIPD is responsible for the system design studies, defining the architecture and coordinating the technical contributions from the other partners. The EARS platform is based on the MP42 bus from Kongsberg Nanoavionics with the addition of two specific modules: an inflatable heat-shield on top and a recovery-propulsion section on the bottom. The propulsion system developed by T4i provides in orbit mobility and precise de-orbiting. The inflatable heat-shield allows for conventional operations during launch and in orbit while guaranteeing a ballistic re-entry with relatively moderate thermomechanical loads. The von Karman Institute is in charge of developing the necessary thermal protections. After parachute deployment, a dedicated GNC unit developed by Deimos guides the parafoil toward a specific direction where the spacecraft is finally recovered in mid-air with a helicopter to avoid impact with the ground or the sea. The capability to recover the payload after each mission also opens up new possibilities to exploit microgravity conditions for scientific research and to produce ultra-pure crystals for several applications including high value sectors like the pharmaceutical and semiconductor ones. The final goal of EARS is to provide an affordable, flexible, frequent, sustainable access to Space for Europe.

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EARS Partners

CNR-IFAC (lead)

DII-UNIPD

Deimos

Von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics

Technology for Propulsion and Innovation

Kongsberg NanoAvionics

Main research topics:

- Chemical Propulsion
- Electric Propulsion
- Plasma Antennas
- Very Low Earth Orbits (VLEO)

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Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This article is part of the EARS project - "European Advanced Reusable Satellite". The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Actions under the HORIZON-CL4-2021-SPACE-01 call, grant agreement No 101082531.